

ON THE USE AND LIMITATIONS OF CONCENTRIC CYLINDER MODELS FOR POLYMER MATRIX COMPOSITES

Edgard Jacobs *, Ignaas Verpoest *, Janis Varna **

* *Department of Metallurgy and Materials Engineering, Katholieke Universiteit Leuven,
de Croylaan 2, B-3001 Heverlee, Belgium*

** *Department of Materials and Production Engineering, Lulea University of Technology,
S-95187 Lulea, Sweden*

SUMMARY: Models to calculate the stiffness matrix of a unidirectional composite involve often the use of a concentric cylinder as unit cell. In this paper, an existing concentric cylinder model of Pagano&Tandon has been extended, by applying the Mori-Tanaka and generalised self-consistent scheme theories to this basic model. The aim is to improve the stiffness prediction for three phase composite systems. It will also be pointed out that, although improvements in stiffness prediction can be achieved, the use of these concentric cylinder models for local stress state analysis in polymer matrix composites is rather questionable.

KEYWORDS: concentric cylinder models, stiffness matrix predictions, local stress state

INTRODUCTION

The determination of the stiffness properties and the local stress state of unidirectional fibre reinforced composites under different loading conditions has already been studied extensively. However, if one wants to point out the influence of a third phase, e.g. a fibre coating, on the overall mechanical properties, very accurate stiffness and strength predictions are required. Several authors have used concentric cylinder models to predict these stiffness and local stress state properties [1-3]. For instance, the effective stiffness matrix of a unidirectional composite can simply be built up, based on 5 independent elastic constants, that completely describe a transversely isotropic material system: the longitudinal E-modulus E_l , the longitudinal Poisson ratio ν_{lt} , the longitudinal shear modulus G_l , the transverse shear modulus G_t and the transverse plane strain bulk modulus k_t . Closed form solutions for these constants are available by models such as the doubly embedded model [4] or the concentric cylinder assemblage model [5]. These models use the basic idea of one concentric cylinder as being a representative unit cell for the unidirectional system.

If however the complete stiffness matrix has to be determined, a combined approach, calculating the complete matrix in one calculation step, is more efficient. Moreover, these models could provide information about the local stress state, given a complex loading situation. Two major calculation methods for this purpose have been presented in literature: the Aboudi (Ab) model [6] and the Pagano&Tandon (PT) model [7]. The former model uses a fibre-coating-matrix system with a rectangular fibre and coating geometry and is therefore, in its basic form, not suitable for local stress predictions. The latter model, on the contrary, makes

use of a concentric fibre-coating-matrix cylinder as unit cell and so called homogeneous boundary conditions of the form $u_i = \varepsilon_{ij}^o * x_j$, which are applied directly at the border of this unit cell. Christensen however showed [8] that the transverse shear modulus of a unidirectional composite can only be well predicted when using a four phase (fibre-coating-matrix-infinitely large composite) concentric cylinder model. So it can be expected that the PT-model, although intrinsically better suitable for local stress predictions, does not give a good prediction of the transverse shear modulus G_t and hence of other elastic constants, dependent on G_t (i.e. the transverse E-modulus E_t and the transverse Poisson ratio ν_{tt}).

In the present work, the use of the Mori-Tanaka (MT) method and the generalised self-consistent scheme (GSCS) method, in combination with the Pagano&Tandon solutions for the displacement components, will be described for composite stiffness matrix predictions.

BASIC CONCEPTS OF THE PAGANO&TANDON MODEL

In order to describe the extensions to the basic PT-model, some key aspects of this model will be first discussed. For a complete description of their *strain based* model, that serves as a basis for further calculations, the reader is referred to [7].

Fig.1: Unit cell in Pagano&Tandon model.

After transformation into cylindrical coordinates, the general form of the applied homogeneous boundary conditions (in the form of displacements $u_i = \varepsilon_{ij}^o * x_j$) is the following:

$$\begin{aligned}
 u_r &= (1/2) * (\varepsilon_{xx}^o - \varepsilon_{yy}^o) * r * \cos(2\theta) + (1/2) * \varepsilon_{xy}^o * r * \sin(2\theta) + (1/2) * (\varepsilon_{xx}^o + \varepsilon_{yy}^o) * r \\
 &\quad + (1/2) * \varepsilon_{zx}^o * z * \cos\theta + (1/2) * \varepsilon_{yz}^o * z * \sin\theta \\
 u_\theta &= (1/2) * \varepsilon_{xy}^o * r * \cos(2\theta) + (1/2) * (\varepsilon_{yy}^o - \varepsilon_{xx}^o) * r * \sin(2\theta) + (1/2) * \varepsilon_{yz}^o * z * \cos\theta \\
 &\quad - (1/2) * \varepsilon_{zx}^o * z * \sin\theta \\
 u_z &= \varepsilon_{zz}^o * z + (1/2) * \varepsilon_{zx}^o * r * \cos\theta + (1/2) * \varepsilon_{yz}^o * r * \sin\theta
 \end{aligned}$$

The nature of the boundary conditions dictates the general form of the solution for the displacement fields and hence for the stress fields. These fields need to be compatible with the applied boundary conditions and the equilibrium equations for the stresses have to be satisfied. The final expressions derived by Pagano&Tandon are of the form:

$$\begin{aligned}
 u_r &= U_1(r) * \cos(2\theta) + U_2(r) * \sin(2\theta) + U_3(r) + U_4(r) * z * \cos\theta + U_5(r) * z * \sin\theta \\
 u_\theta &= V_1(r) * \sin(2\theta) + V_2(r) * \cos(2\theta) + V_4(r) * z * \sin\theta + V_5(r) * z * \cos\theta \\
 u_z &= W_3(r) * z + W_4(r) * \cos\theta + W_5(r) * \sin\theta
 \end{aligned}$$

The r-dependent functions in these expressions, $U_i(r)$, $V_i(r)$ and $W_i(r)$, are mentioned in [7]. The only adaptation, the current authors made, is putting $F_4=F_3$ and $H_4=H_3$ in order to satisfy the set of equilibrium equations in all cases. By satisfying continuity of displacements and tractions across the fibre-coating and coating-matrix interfaces, demanding that stresses and displacements must be bounded at the fibre origin and specifying the externally applied strain components, Pagano&Tandon proved that all unknown constants in the above displacement expressions can be determined.

With a specimen subjected to homogeneous boundary conditions of the form $u_i = \epsilon_{ij}^o * x_j$ over its entire surface, it can be shown that the volumetric average strain over the specimen ϵ_{ij} is equal to ϵ_{ij}^o [5]; moreover, the strain energy, stored in the representative volume element, is given by $(1/2) * \sigma'_{ij} * \epsilon'_{ij}$ with σ'_{ij} the volumetric average stress. As for a homogeneous material, this strain energy equals $(1/2) * \sigma_{ij}^o * \epsilon_{ij}^o$ and as by definition $\sigma_{ij}^o = C_{ij}^o * \epsilon_{ij}^o$ ($C_{ij}^o =$ effective composite stiffness matrix), the previous relations lead to the simple relation $\sigma'_{ij} = \sigma_{ij}^o$.

In other words, *if* the stresses and strains inside the body can be *exactly* determined, a composite stiffness matrix can be easily calculated. For example, by considering the external strain state $\epsilon_{ij}^o = [1;0;0;0;0;0]$ and solving the unknown constants of the model, the 6 volumetric average composite stresses σ'_{ij} ($=\sigma_{ij}^o$) can be calculated and these values represent the first column of the composite stiffness matrix C_{ij}^o . In the same way, the other columns of the stiffness matrix can be determined.

The above procedure has been followed by Pagano&Tandon to determine the complete stiffness matrix of two phase unidirectional composites. The final stiffness matrix, calculated from a strain based model, is a lower bound of the real solution. In an analogous way, Pagano&Tandon derived a corresponding stress based model (homogeneous boundary conditions in the form of tractions) [9]. The results of this model finally lead to an upper bound of the exact stiffness matrix. Gardner and Pittman [10] however pointed out that, in the case of a three phase composite system with a very compliant fibre coating, these lower and upper bound predictions can be far different. This is the case for the transverse shear modulus component G_t , the transverse E-modulus E_t and the transverse Poisson ratio ν_{tt} as pointed out in the introduction. Further model improvements are consequently necessary in order to closely predict all engineering constants.

MORI-TANAKA METHOD, APPLIED TO PT-MODEL

A first extension of the basic Pagano&Tandon model involves the use of the Mori-Tanaka theory [11]. Following this theory, local fields in a coated inclusion can be approximately determined by fields found when the coated inclusion is embedded in an unbounded matrix medium, subjected to the average matrix strains (or stresses) at infinity. This approximation is especially valid for low fibre volume fractions. The advantage of the approach is that the local fields in the coating and the inclusion, and in the adjacent matrix can be evaluated by using the solution of a single coated particle in an infinite matrix and *particle interaction* is implicitly taken into account through the yet unknown average matrix stresses.

In other words, a coated inclusion is surrounded by an infinitely long matrix area and at the border of this matrix zone a displacement field of the form $u_i = \epsilon_{ij}^m * x_j$ is applied. The value of ϵ_{ij}^m , which is now the average strain in the matrix since an infinitely long matrix zone is considered, is unknown; it has to be determined so that the volumetric average composite strains $\epsilon'_{ij} = \sum_k V_k * \epsilon_{ij}^k = \epsilon_{ij}^o$ (applied external strains).

Fig.2: Mori-Tanaka method: inclusion in unbounded matrix

The analysis is schematically shown below:

Scheme of Mori-Tanaka analysis

By relating the volumetric average stresses to the volumetric average strains in each component and by using the relation $\sigma'_{ij} = \sigma^o_{ij}$, the composite stress components can be evaluated for given external strain values ϵ^o_{ij} . Also, in this method, the composite stiffness matrix is built up column by column.

GENERALISED SELF-CONSISTENT SCHEME METHOD, APPLIED TO PT-MODEL

The two beforementioned methods both have some shortcomings. The basic PT stress and strain based models can lead to big differences in the predicted stiffness or engineering values. Their results are as accurate as the ones of the concentric cylinder model. The MT-model predicts values within the PT upper and lower bounds, but - for higher fibre volume fractions - the assumption of a coated inclusion embedded in an *infinite* matrix zone becomes less accurate.

A more representative model consists of a concentric fibre-coating-matrix cylinder, surrounded by an infinite equivalent composite area. Christensen [8] used this geometry to calculate the composite transverse shear modulus and his predictions are regarded to be the most accurate of all existing models. As the stiffness properties of the equivalent composite zone are the additional unknowns in this type of analysis, additional relations are required to solve the problem. Christensen's additional relation stated that the strain energy, stored in a homogeneous composite medium under applied displacement conditions, has to be equal to the strain energy of the model, containing a fibre-coating-matrix inclusion in the same homogeneous medium under the same displacement conditions.

Fig.3: Generalised self-consistent scheme model

We further adapted the basic PT-model to the Christensen geometry. This adaptation includes an extension from the MT-model (=fibre-coating-infinite matrix model) to a fibre-coating-matrix-infinite composite model. The additional strain energy relation in the Christensen model is however not sufficient if one wants to determine the complete stiffness matrix. For a transversely isotropic material system, the latter namely requires 5 additional relations for the 5 unknown independent elastic properties. Therefore, the MT-solution has been used as initial input data for the composite stiffness matrix and the final solution has been calculated by an iterative procedure. The analysis is again schematically shown below.

It should be noted that, with this iterative procedure, the derived value for the composite transverse shear modulus is exactly the same as the prediction of the Christensen model; this is true while at convergency the strain energy in the four phase model equals the strain energy of the homogeneous composite model, which is exactly the additional relation used by Christensen.

Overview of generalised self-consistent scheme analysis

RESULTS FOR CARBON-EPOXY UNIDIRECTIONAL COMPOSITES

In order to compare the predictions of the Mori-Tanaka (MT) model and the generalised self-consistent scheme (GSCS) model with those of the Pagano&Tandon stress (PT-stress) and strain (PT-strain) based models and the Aboudi (Ab) model, calculations have been performed for a unidirectional composite, as used in the Gardner&Pittman article [10]. This composite system involves carbon fibre, elastomeric interphase and epoxy matrix constituents with the following properties:

Table 1: Constituent properties of three phase composite

Constituents	E_l (GPa)	E_t (GPa)	ν_{lt}	ν_{tt}	G_t (GPa)
Carbon fibre	380	6.2	0.2	0.25	7.6
Interphase	0.005	0.005	0.4	0.4	$E_l / (2*(1+\nu_{lt}))$
Epoxy matrix	3.4	3.4	0.35	0.35	$E_l / (2*(1+\nu_{lt}))$

The fibre volume fraction has been fixed at 50%. Predictions for the transverse Young's modulus E_t , the transverse shear modulus G_t and the transverse Poisson ratio ν_{tt} are presented in Figs. 4-6 as a function of the coating thickness. It can be concluded that, at this fibre volume fraction, the Mori-Tanaka stiffness predictions are always close to the strain based Pagano&Tandon solution. The generalised self-consistent scheme theory predicts values that lie well within the upper and lower bounds for small interphase thicknesses and seem to approach the stress based Pagano&Tandon solutions for thick coatings. This conclusion contrasts with that of Gardner&Pittman, who found for their Aboudi model solutions that

approximate the stress based Pagano&Tandon results at small values of the interphase thickness, whereas for thicker interphases the results approach the strain based Pagano&Tandon solution.

Fig.4: Transverse shear modulus of a three phase composite (see Table1) vs coating thickness

Fig.5: Transverse Young's modulus of a three phase composite (see Table1) vs coating thickness

Calculations have further been performed for a three phase unidirectional composite with an intermediate modulus carbon fibre and with a standard fibre volume fraction of 60%. The constituent properties are summarized in Table 2. A volume fraction of 10% for the interphase has been used and the stiffness of the interphase varied between 0.01GPa and 10GPa.

Table 2: Constituent properties of three phase composite with intermediate modulus C-fibre.

Constituents	E_l (GPa)	E_t (GPa)	ν_{lt}	ν_{tt}	G_l (GPa)
Carbon fibre	230	13.8	0.22	0.37	18
Interphase	0.01-10	0.01-10	0.35	0.35	$E_l / (2*(1+\nu_{lt}))$
Epoxy matrix	3.2	3.2	0.35	0.35	$E_l / (2*(1+\nu_{lt}))$

Engineering constants for the strain based PT-model, the MT-model and the GSCS-model are shown in Figs. 7-9. It can be found that, for a wide range of coating stiffness values, the difference in these model predictions are not so significant. However, for a very low coating stiffness (clearly lower than 0.1GPa for this unidirectional system), both the basic Pagano&Tandon strain based model and the Mori-Tanaka extension start to predict transverse

shear moduli and transverse Young's moduli that are relatively higher than the generalised self-consistent scheme result. As a result, the predictions of the transverse Poisson ratio start to deviate from the exact solution for these models.

Fig. 6: Transverse Poisson ratio of a three phase composite (see Table1) vs coating thickness

It can therefore be concluded that, for a three phase system with a very compliant interphase, the generalised self-consistent scheme method has to be used in order to correctly predict these transverse properties. Or, if one wants to use three phase expressions for separate engineering constants, the Christensen model should here be used for the transverse shear modulus.

Fig.7: Transverse shear modulus of a three phase composite (see Table2) vs coating stiffness

The above conclusions are based on the prediction of engineering constants of unidirectional composites. These models however also finally provide information about the local stress state in the composite unit cell. In the case of pure transverse loading of a unidirectional system, the maximum principal stress in the matrix is often used [12,13] to indicate stress concentrations occurring in the composite. These stress concentrations give - for brittle fiber, brittle matrix systems - already a good indication of transverse failure. For a *two* phase carbon-epoxy composite with constituent properties mentioned in Table 2, this maximum principal stress has been calculated for the basic PT strain based model, for the GSCS model and their results compared with those of finite element calculations, assuming a hexagonal unit cell (Fig. 10). The finite element calculations have been performed as described in the article of Achenbach&Zhu [14].

Fig. 8: Transverse Young's modulus of a three phase composite (see Table2) vs coating stiffness

Fig. 9: Transverse Poisson ratio of a three phase composite (see Table2) vs coating stiffness

Fig. 10 : Matrix stress magnification factor vs fibre volume fraction for a two phase composite (see Table2)

It can be concluded that, although these concentric cylinder models give quite accurate predictions of the composite stiffness matrix, local stress information is much less accurate. This is related to on one hand the use of a concentric cylinder as representative volume element and on the other hand the use of very simplified homogeneous boundary conditions in these concentric cylinder models. Although Pagano&Tandon mention that these concentric cylinder models give sufficiently accurate stress predictions for metal and ceramic matrix composites,

the authors believe that, for *polymer matrix composites* with a big difference in fibre and matrix stiffness, these models are not sufficiently accurate and need to be improved in order to give additional information about e.g. von Mises or principal stresses. An improved model has therefore been developed by the current authors and model concepts will be discussed in a future paper.

CONCLUSION

The Pagano&Tandon model to calculate the stiffness matrix of a unidirectional composite has been extended into two new models. The first involves the Mori-Tanaka theory, applied to the Pagano&Tandon model; this extension does not lead to profound changes in stiffness predictions. The second extension involves the generalised self-consistent scheme theory, applied to the Pagano&Tandon model; here, an improvement in stiffness prediction can be achieved, especially for three phase systems with a very compliant interphase. None of these concentric cylinder models are however sufficiently accurate to give detailed information about the local stresses in the unit cell for a given applied load.

REFERENCES

1. Hashin, Z., "Analysis of properties of fiber composites with anisotropic constituents", *J. Appl. Mech.*, Vol.46, 1979, pp. 543-550.
2. Zhao, X. and Chen, W.F., "The effective elastic moduli of concrete and composite materials", *Composites PartB*, Vol.29B, 1998, pp. 31-40.
3. Carman, G.P., Averill, R.C., Reifsnider, K.L. and Reddy, J.N., "Optimization of fiber coatings to minimize stress concentrations in composite materials", *J. Comp. Materials*, Vol.27, No.6, 1993, pp. 589-611.
4. Hermans, J.J., "The elastic properties of fiber reinforced materials when the fibers are aligned", *Proc. K. Ned. Akad. Wet. B*, Vol.70, No.1, 1967, pp.1-9.
5. Hashin, Z., "The elastic moduli of fiber-reinforced materials", *J. Appl. Mech.*, Vol.31, 1964, pp. 223-232.
6. Aboudi, J., "Mechanics of composite materials: a unified micromechanical approach", Elsevier, New York, 1991.
7. Pagano, N.J. and Tandon, G.P., "Elastic response of multi-directional coated-fiber composites", *Comp. Sci&Technol.*, Vol.31, 1988, pp. 273-293.
8. Christensen, R.M. and Lo, K.H., "Solutions for effective shear properties in three phase sphere and cylinder models", *J. Mech. Phys. Solids*, Vol.27, 1979, pp. 315-330.
9. Pagano, N.J. and Tandon, G.P., "Thermo-elastic model for multidirectional coated-fiber composites: traction formulation", *Comp. Sci&Technol.*, Vol.38, No3, 1990, pp.247-269.
10. Gardner, S.D., Pittman, C.U. and Hackett, R.M., "Polymeric composite materials incorporating an elastomeric interphase: a mathematical assessment", *Comp. Sci&Technol.*, Vol.46, 1993, pp. 307-318.
11. Benveniste, Y., Dvorak, G.J. and Chen, T., "Stress fields in composites with coated inclusions", *Mech. of Materials*, Vol.7, 1989, pp. 305-317.
12. Adams, D.F. and Doner, D.R., "Transverse normal loading of a unidirectional composite", *J. Comp. Mat.*, Vol.1, 1967, pp. 4.
13. Skudra, A.H. and Bulavs, F.YA., "Structural theory of reinforced plastics", Riga.
14. Achenbach, J.D. and Zhu, H., "Effect of interfacial zone on mechanical behavior and failure of fiber-reinforced composites", *J. Mech. Phys. Solids*, Vol.37, No.3, 1989, pp. 381-393.